

Protein content variation among rice varieties

M. Jayapragasam, A. Manickam, N. M. Ahamad, and B. Thayumanavan, Biochemistry Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We analyzed the grain of 294 rice genotypes raised in the same field under similar cultural operations for protein content, using conventional micro-Kjeldahl method. Grain samples were dehusked by hand-pounding. Brown rice protein content was expressed as dry weight % after multiplying by 5.95.

Total protein varied from 4.94% in Ratna and Sona to 12.86% in ADT21. ASD10, T3 (Tainan), and T8 had protein contents higher than 12%. Thirty samples contained more than 10% protein; 112 samples, 8-10%; 137 samples, 6-8%; and 15 samples, less than 6%. Ten of 40 ADT varieties had more than 10% protein. TKM and ADT

Mean and dispersal coefficient of variation of protein content of grain of some rice varieties. Tamil Nadu, India.

Varieties	Soluble protein			Total protein		
	Samples (no.)	Mean (%)	CV (%)	Samples (no.)	Mean (%)	CV (%)
ADT varieties	39	0.51	63.3	40	9.08	17.9
ASD varieties	18	0.97	38.7	18	8.87	18.7
CO varieties	18	0.68	36.8	28	8.11	12.8
CO32 mutants	4	0.56	24.3	4	7.32	14.6
CO33 mutants	10	0.81	32.3	10	8.50	18.8
IR varieties	6	0.48	37.3	8	7.18	12.1
Ponni/IR8 (F ₄)	—	—	—	39	8.45	5.5
Tainan varieties	50	1.05	30.0	50	8.74	16.1
TKM varieties	8	0.89	39.7	8	9.10	17.4
TKM6 mutants	11	1.00	24.0	11	7.64	20.8
Other varieties	77	0.57	40.4	78	7.62	17.3
All genotypes	241	0.74	48.2	294	8.26	17.2

varieties had the highest average protein content, 9.1%.

Hot-water soluble protein estimated colorimetrically by Lowry's method showed greater variation than total protein (see table). The Tainan types had the highest average soluble protein content (1.05%). Total protein and soluble protein contents of the grain

were not significantly correlated. Protein of 62 varieties soluble in 0.1 M NaOH and determined by Lowry's method was very highly significantly correlated with micro-Kjeldahl protein ($r = 0.93^{**}$). The coefficient of variation for data from Lowry's method (18.11%) was slightly lower than that for the micro-Kjeldahl method (19.41%). □

Disease resistance

Multiple resistance to bacterial blight (BB) and four fungal diseases

R. N. Singh and A. T. Khan, N. D. University of Agriculture and Technology, P. O. Dabha Semar, District Faizabad 224133, U. P. India

We tested 233 rice varieties and lines in the 1986 National Screening Nursery and Multiple Resistance Screening Trial for resistance to BB, sheath rot (ShR), brown spot (BS), false smut (FS), and narrow brown leaf spot (NBLs) diseases during 1986-87 wet season. Each test entry was planted in 2-m-long rows at 20 × 15-cm spacing.

Plants in half of the rows were clip-inoculated with a suspension of a local isolate of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye at maximum tillering. BB was rated at 15 and 30 d after inoculation. Reactions to high natural BS, NBLs, ShR, and FS disease

Resistance of varieties and lines to BB, ShR, BS, FS, and NBLs.^a Uttar Pradesh, India, 1986-87 wet season.

Disease	Varieties (%)			
	Disease-free	Resistant	Moderately susceptible	Susceptible
BB	0	42.0	47.2	10.7
ShR	0.4	45.4	48.5	5.6
BS	0	23.2	73.0	3.9
FS	26.2	43.0	24.0	6.8
NBLs	65.7	3.4	13.7	17.2

^aData based on 233 varieties except for FS and NBLs, where observations were recorded on 221 and 231 lines, respectively.

pressure were taken on plants in the other half of the rows.

No variety or line escaped BB and BS (see table). Only one remained free of ShR; 26.2% escaped FS. Because NBLs appeared late in the season, a majority of the varieties (65.67%) escaped the disease; however, the highest number of entries showed susceptibility. More varieties showed resistance to ShR (45.45%) and moderate susceptibility to BS (72.96%); fewer were resistant (3.43%) and moderately susceptible (13.74%) to NBLs.

IET8958, IET9313, IET9843, and

IR50 showed multiple resistance to BB, ShR, BS, and FS; IET8340 showed resistance to BB, ShR, FS, and NBLs. Entries with multiple resistance to three diseases included IET7511, IET7720, IET7978, RP16691-2897-5526, and IR29652-65-2-3 to ShR, BS, and FS; IET8022, IET8023, IET9965, and IR32429-45-3-2-6 to BB, ShR, and BS; IET8364, IET8653, IET8611, and IET9799 to BB, BS, and FS; and IET8588 to ShR, FS, and NBLs. A large number of entries possess resistance to two diseases, many others are resistant to one disease. □